

PROBLEMS, CHALLENGES AND COPING MECHANISM OF THE SELECTED ASSATIDZ AND STUDENTS IN JA'MIATUL WAQF AS AN AFTERMATH OF MARAWI SIEGE

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 24

Issue 3

Pages: 311-318

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2262

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13371377

Manuscript Accepted: 07-12-2024

Problems, Challenges and Coping Mechanism of the Selected Assatidz and Students in Ja'miatul Waqf as an Aftermath of Marawi Siege

Arsalan A. Diamoaden*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to find out the Problems, Challenges, and coping Mechanisms of the Select Students and Asaatidz of Ja'miatul Waqf in the aftermath of the Marawi Siege. It attempted to find answers to the following queries: (1) what is the Demographic Profile of the respondents in terms of Age, Sex, Civil Status, Educational Attainment, Ethnic Affiliation, and Monthly Income? (2) What are the Problems and Challenges Confronting the selected Assatidz and Students in the aftermath of the Marawi Siege in terms of Psycho-Social, Living Condition, Financial, and Health Conditions? (3) What are the Coping Mechanisms of the Selected Assatidz and Students of Ja'miatul Waqf in the aftermath of the Marawi siege in terms of Education, Adaptation, Acceptance, Open-Mindedness, and satisfaction of Basic Needs? The study utilized the Inferential research design that made use of both descriptive qualitative and correlation quantitative approaches in the interpretation of data gathered as well as information regarding the Problem, Challenges, and Coping Mechanism of the selected Assatidz and Students of Ja'miatul Waqf as an aftermath of Marawi Siege. The principal aim of employing this method is to describe the nature of the situation as it exists at the time of the study and to explore the Problems, Challenges, and Coping mechanisms of the respondents. The 100 respondents were the 10 Selected Assatidz, 40 College Students (Khuliyah), and 50 High School Students (Thanawe). The respondents were all based in Marawi City. Further, statistical tools, such as the chi-square independent test, the frequency and percentage distribution, and the measure of central tendency (weighted mean), were utilized in order to achieve the objectives of this study. The significant findings of this study are the following: (1) Majority of the respondents are Meranaw females aged between 18 to 22 years old and some high school students. Most of them are single with monthly income below 5,000 or none at all. (2) The respondent's responses to the problems, challenges, and coping mechanisms in terms of psycho-social, living conditions, finances, and health presented by the researchers are shown in the table below. The respondents agreed on the Psycho-social and financial, while they neither agreed nor disagreed on the living conditions and health that the statement presented by the researcher is the problems and challenges that they faced after the Marawi siege. On the other hand, they agreed on the psycho-social, living conditions, and health, while they neither agreed nor disagreed that the statements presented by the researcher are their coping mechanism toward problems and challenges. (3) Based on the computed Square Independent Test, there is a significant relationship between the problem and challenges towards their coping mechanism in terms of psychosocial, living conditions, finances, and health.

Keywords: *problems, challenges, coping mechanisms*

Introduction

The Madaris Education in Marawi City was put in a bad light after people saw that there were minor members of the Maute Group enrolled in the Madaris School. In fact, it was claimed that many Madaris Schools or "Torrel" were considered as training grounds for terrorist and extremist groups as many of the so-called "Child Warriors" were from these Madrasah/Torrel accordingly. Thus, the Local Official of Marawi alleged and criticized the Madaris Curriculum as a motivating factor for youngsters to join terrorism.

The five-month Marawi siege between the Philippine Armed Forces and the ISIS-inspired Maute group brought the masjid and madrasah and other properties into ruins with no remnants than ashes. However, the Present Duterte administration promised to rebuild the Islamic City. However, there is no assurance that belongings or Properties will be included in the proposed renovation proposal on the grounds that these are not constitutionally considered part of the government assets. It will be the obligation of the people in the Islamic City of Marawi, particularly the Local Government Unit and the religious organizations, to work together and find ways to renovate and revive the destroyed masjid, madrasah, buildings, and other related belongings. The Researcher spearheads the Study to Investigate the Concrete Difficulties, Challenges, and Coping Mechanisms of Certain Students and Assatidz of Ja'miatul Waqf in the Aftermath of the Marawi Siege. For this, the researcher decided to pursue it as the central focus of this current study.

As observations and experiences of internally displaced persons, the following are the sentiments of the Select Assatidz and Students of Ja'miatul Waqf after the Marawi Siege to wit: Displacement of Livelihood, Psychological Trauma, Misconception to the Curriculum of Arabic Institutions, Misconception of the Niqabi, Feeling Loss, and affliction, Anguish, Despondent, Resentment, Displacement of Minor and Major Madrasah.

Hence, this study aimed to Investigate the actual problem, challenges, and coping mechanism of the select Assatidz and Students of Ja'miatul Waqf in the Aftermath of the Marawi Siege. The study's concern is the hope to give people an overview of the strategies of the teachers and students of the Madarish, like the Ja'miatul Waqf, in coping with what happened to them after the siege.

Research Questions

Generally, this Study attempted to determine the problems, challenges, and coping mechanisms of the selected Assatidz and students of Ja'miatul Waqf in the Aftermath of the Marawi Siege. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the Demographic profiles of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. civil status;
 - 1.4. educational attainment;
 - 1.5. ethnic affiliation; and
 - 1.6. monthly income?
2. What are the Problem and challenges confronting the selected Asaatidz and Students as an aftermath of Marawi siege in terms of:
 - 2.1. psycho-social;
 - 2.2. living condition;
 - 2.3. financial; and
 - 2.4. health condition?
3. What are the coping mechanism of the Selected Asaatidz and Students of Ja'miatul Waqf as an aftermath of the Siege in terms of:
 - 3.1. education;
 - 3.2. adaptation;
 - 3.3. acceptance;
 - 3.4. open-mindedness; and
 - 3.5. satisfaction of basic needs?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the Qualitative descriptive survey research design that made use of qualitative descriptive in the analysis of data. The principal aim in employing this method is to describe the nature of situation as it exists at the time of the study and to explore problem, challenges and coping mechanism of the respondents.

Respondents

The study involved the Select Assatidz and students of Ja'miatul Waqf as respondents who are the ones primarily affected by the Marawi siege. The researcher was supposed to gather data from a target number of respondents. There were one hundred (100) respondents of the study. The selected respondents are the following to wit; 1. forty (40) (Khuliyah) College Students, 2. Fifty (50) (Thanawe) High School Students and 3. Ten (10) Asaatidz of Ja'miatul Waqf.

The study first utilized purposive sampling in that only those students and Assatidz of Ja'miatul Waqf located at Barangay Cadayunan II, Marawi City. Next systematic random sampling was used to get the 40 college students and 50 high school students. Complete enumeration was used for the 10 Assatidz(teacher). And finally to pick up the number of students from college and high school a simple random method by raffles style was utilized.

Instrument

The main research instruments used in gathering data was self- designed questionnaire. It was divided into 3 parts: Part One was the socio-Demographic Profile of the respondents; and Part two was the problem, challenges and coping mechanism of the Selected assatidz and students of Ja'miatul Waqf as an Aftermath of Marawi Siege. Part three was the coping mechanism of the selected Asaatidz and Students of Ja'miatul Waqf as an aftermath of Marawi Siege.

Procedure

Data obtained were in the form of primary data. Primary data are those directly taken from the field. Before the conduct of the Study, letters were prepared and sent to the selected Assatidz and Students in Ja'miatul Waqf to allow the conduct of the data gathering through questionnaire. Questionnaires were given to the respondents in the month of April 7, 2018. Furthermore, the researcher further explained the intention of conducting the study with much concerned to the respondent's perception towards this study.

Data Analysis

To accomplish the objective of the study, cross sectional survey was used to summarize the socio-demographic data into a simpler summary to make it easier to understand and interpret and investigate the respondents' answers on Problems, Challenges and Coping Mechanism on the Selected Students and Assatidz of Ja'miatul Waqf as an aftermath of Marawi siege. With the use of a self-made

questionnaire the numbers of questions were integrated by the researcher the questionnaire was also checked and validated, the answers of the respondents were tabulated and analyzed using the statistical tools such as: frequency and percentage for the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their Age, Sex, Civil Status, Educational Attainment, Ethnic Affiliation, Monthly Income. Also, Corresponding Mean and Weighted Mean were applied to treat data relative to the responses of the respondents as it deemed applicable.

Results and Discussion

Respondents Profile

The following tables show the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondent's profiles in terms of age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, ethnic affiliation, and monthly income.

Respondents' Age

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents by age.

Table 1. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents Age*

Age	Student		Teacher	
	Freq. (f)	%	Freq. (f)	%
18-22 years old	54	54%	0	0%
23-27 years old	34	34%	0	0%
28-32 years old	1	1%	0	0%
33-37 years old	1	1%	0	0%
38-42 years old	0	0%	1	1%
43-47 years old	0	0%	1	1%
48-52 years old	0	0%	2	2%
Above 52 years old	0	0%	6	6%
Total	90	100%	10	100%

Legend: f = Frequency; % = Percentage

Table 1 presents that 54% of the respondents students age within the interval 18 to 22 years old, 34% of the respondents whose age are within 23 to 27 years old, then for the following age interval 28 to 32, 33 to 37, 38 to 42, and 43 to 52, each has 1% of the total number of respondents. While for the respondent teachers/ Assatidz their age 6% fall between 52 and above and the remaining 2% were in the age bracket between 48-52 years old interval.

As depicted in the table that majority (54%) of the respondents students falls within the age bracket of 18-22 years olds and many (34%) also were in the age bracket 23-27, which imply that they are young adults, living an active life as students. On the other hand for the Assatidz (teacher), majority (6%) of them were within the age bracket of 52 and above and only few (2%) were between 48-52 interval which signifies that they were matured and responsible individuals.

Respondents Sex

Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to their sex.

Table 2. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents Sex*

Sex	Student		Teacher	
	Freq. (f)	%	Freq. (f)	%
Male	40	40%	7	70%
Female	50	50%	3	30%
Total	90	100%	10	100%

Legend: f = Frequency; % = Percentage

Table 2 shows the respondents distribution of their sex. As glimpsed from the table that 40% of the student respondents are male while another 50% are female. In the same table it can be seen that for the respondents teachers, 7% of them are male and 3% are female.

The findings depicted that for the student's majority (50%) were female and also many (40%) were male. Time and again in many research output it proves always that in today's society female outnumbered their male counterpart. However, the data also indicate that for the respondent's teacher, majority (7%) were male and only few (3%) were female. This finding is contrary to the majority research output when it comes to sex, female dominate the male but in the case of the respondent teachers, male dominates the population. This could be attributed to the fact that learned Ulamas put premium to male populace as they want to promote a patriarchal society.

Respondents Civil Status

Table 3 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents civil status.

Table 3. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents Civil Status*

Civil Status	Student		Teacher	
	Freq. (f)	%	Freq. (f)	%
Single	82	82%	0	0%
Married	8	8%	10	10%
Widow	0	0%	0	0%
Separated/divorce	0	0%	0	0%
Total	90	100%	10	100%

Legend: f = Frequency; % = Percentage

Table 3 shows the respondents distribution by civil status, as reflected in the table that 82 of the student respondents are single while 8% of them are married. However for the teacher respondents is 100% meaning all of them were married.

The data implied that majority of those student respondent were single and only a few (8%) were married. This is expected as students don't want to be burdened with raising a family while they are schooling. But in the case of the teacher respondents, with their age, it is expected that they have family of their own.

Respondents Educational Attainment

Table 4 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents educational attainment.

Table 4. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondent's Educational Attainment*

Educational Attainment	Student		Teacher	
	Freq. (f)	%	Freq. (f)	%
High School level (Thanawe)	50	50%	0	0%
College Level (Kulliyah)	40	40%	1	10%
Bachelor's Degree	0	0%	6	60%
Master's Degree	0	0%	3	30%
Doctorate Degree	0	0%	0	0%
Total	90	100%	10	100%

Legend: f = Frequency; % = Percentage

Table 4 shows the respondents' distribution on educational attainment. The table reflects that 50% of the student respondents were still in Thanawe (Secondary) while 40% were college. The data seen in the table displays that for the Assatidz (teacher) 6% of them were with bachelor's degree, 3% were master's degree holders, and 1% is with college degree.

The findings indicate that for the student respondents all of them did not yet finish a degree as they were still schooling. While for the respondent teachers majority (60%) of them were bachelor degree, some (30%) were Masters' degree holder and only one (10%) depicted that he was still in the college level. The findings further implied that teachers also in Madrasah were competitive to teach.

Respondents Ethnic Affiliation

Table 5 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents ethnic affiliation.

Table 5. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents Ethnic Affiliation*

Ethnic Affiliation	Student		Teacher	
	Freq. (f)	%	Freq. (f)	%
Meranaw	89	89%	10	100%
Maguindanao	1	10%	0	0%
Iranun	0	0%	0	0%
Tausug	0	0%	0	0%
Total	90	90%	10	100%

Legend: f = Frequency; % = Percentage

Table 5 shows the respondents distribution of ethnic affiliation. As seen from the table above that 89% of students respondent were Meranaws and only 10% was Maguindanaon. However for the teacher respondents, including 100% they are all Meranaw.

The findings denote that Meranaw tribe dominates the population of the setting of the students. This also indicated that for the teachers of the setting of the study, it reflected a 100% Meranaw. Although for the students there is one Maguinadanaon. This also indicates that as expected since the school is located in Marawi where most of the population were Meranaw.

Respondents Monthly Income

Table 6 shows frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents' monthly income.

Table 6. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents Monthly Income*

Monthly Income	Student		Teacher	
	Freq. (f)	%	Freq. (f)	%
None or below 5,000	59	59%	0	0%
Php 5,000 to Php 9,999	27	27%	0	0%
Php 10,000 to Php 14,999	3	3%	0	0%
Php 15,000 to Php 19,999	0	0%	0	0%
Php 20,000 to Php 24,999	0	0%	1	1%
Php 25,000 and above	0	0%	9	9%
Total	90	90%	10	10%

Legend: f = Frequency; % = Percentage

Table 6 shows the respondent's distribution of Monthly Income. As shown in the table that 59% of the student respondents have an income of below 5,000, 27% of the 90 respondents have monthly income that falls within the interval of 5,000 to 9,999 pesos and 3% falls within the income interval of 10,000 to 14,999 pesos. While for the teacher respondents 90% of the 10 have a monthly income within 25,000 and above and 10% of them have a monthly income within 20,000 to 24,999 pesos.

The findings seen in the table depicted the majority of the respondent students which have low income which is expected because they were students. The findings in the table also denote that for the Assatidz/teachers, they have higher income which at present high cost of living may not be sufficient to support a big family.

The Problems and Challenges Among Select Asaatidz and Students after the Marawi Siege

The second part of the research instruments is concerned with determining the respondents' difficulties they faced after the Marawi siege. There are four (4) indicators such as Psycho-social, Living Condition, Financial and Health each consists of sub-indicators in this part of the questionnaire.

Psycho-Social, Living Condition, Financial and Health Problem and Challenges of the Respondent.

Table 7 displays the summary of the weighted mean and standard deviation of the Psycho-Social, Living Condition, Financial and Health Problem and challenges as perceived by the respondents.

Table 7. *Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation of the Psycho-Social, Living Condition, Financial and Health as Difficulties of the Respondents*

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Remark
Psycho-Social			
1	2.85	23.08	Agree
2	3.00	20.02	Neutral
3	3.06	15.70	Neutral
4	2.73	17.83	Neutral
5	2.45	17.85	Agree
Grand Mean	2.82	18.77	Agree
Living Condition			
1	3.85	25.17	Disagree
2	3.32	20.90	Neutral
3	2.97	14.39	Neutral
Grand Mean	3.38	20.15	Neutral
Financial			
1	1.89	22.08	Agree
2	2.26	13.77	Agree
3	2.11	19.74	Agree
4	2.33	14.37	Agree
Grand Mean	2.15	17.49	Agree
Health			
1	3.07	21.55	Neutral
2	2.98	19.29	Neutral
3	2.73	20.92	Neutral
Grand Mean	2.93	20.59	Neutral

Legend: 1 = Certainly Agree; 2 = Agree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = Disagree; 5 = Certainly Disagree

Table 7 shows the weighted means and standard deviations of the respondents' perceptions on the Psycho-Social, Living Condition, Financial and Health as the problems and challenges they faced after the Marawi Siege. As seen in the table the grand mean obtain in Psycho-Social challenges and problem is 2.82 with a standard deviation of 18.77 interpreted as agree. As to living condition, it garnered a grand mean of 3.38 with a standard deviation of 20.15, interpreted as neutral. While on financial challenges and problem it garnered a grand mean of 2.15 with a standard deviation of 17.49, interpreted as agree. And on health, it has a grand mean of 2.93 with a standard

deviation of 20.59, interpreted as neutral.

As indicated in the data that respondent agreed that they faced Psycho-social and financial difficulties. This implied that the respondents were undergoing challenges because of the insufficiency of financial support as a result of the lack of livelihood to satisfy the need of the family. In the same manner as they also faced some psycho-social problem/Challenges because of their traumatic experience during the siege. It is but natural to be stressed and suffering anxiety if you are a victim of terrorism. However, the respondents in Living Condition and Health response is neutral meaning they neither agree nor disagree that these variables contributed to their difficulties in their life after the siege. The findings implied that the respondents living condition and health are only considered by them as secondary. Further, the respondents have a full acceptance of the shelter provided and their health condition as they struggle how to sustain their daily sustenance.

The finding is congruent to the article of Women's and children's rights violations Gabriela Women's Partylist Rep. Arlene Brosas that states that children and women residents of Marawi City suffered from economic insecurities, as a direct result of the government's aerial bombings that left workplaces destroyed or abandoned.

"Walang wala kaming pera dito," (We have no money here at all) she quoted a Marawi evacuee being interviewed. Many evacuation centers lacked even basic necessities such as running water for washing clothes and bathing, sanitary items, electricity, and in some cases, food and drinking water. There are no facilities for pregnant women. There is a lack of sanitary toilet and bathroom.

She added that many residents, especially the children, are in dire need of mental health treatment to help them cope with stress and anxieties. She noted that the government has little effort to address this so far.

Coping Mechanism of selected Assatidz and Students after the Marawi Siege

The third part of the research instruments is concerned with determining the respondents' coping mechanisms towards the problems and challenges they faced after the Marawi siege. There are four (4) indicators such as Psycho-social, Living Condition, Financial and Health each consists of sub-indicators in this part of the questionnaire.

Table 8. *Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation of the Psycho-Social, Living Condition, Financial and Health as a Coping Mechanism of the Respondents*

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Remark
Psycho-Social			
1	3.22	12.10	Neutral
2	1.66	23.41	Certainly agree
3	1.43	27.29	Certainly agree
4	1.48	26.23	Certainly agree
Grand Mean	1.95	22.23	Agree
Living Condition			
1	2.47	17.22	Agree
2	2.16	26.61	Agree
3	2.54	20.77	Agree
Grand Mean	2.39	21.53	Agree
Financial			
1	3.19	15.36	Neutral
2	2.58	17.04	Agree
3	3.39	12.63	Neutral
Grand Mean	3.05	15.01	Neutral
Health			
1	1.83	18.88	Agree
2	1.86	18.41	Agree
3	1.80	19.47	Agree
4	3.57	20.54	Disagree
Grand Mean	2.27	19.33	Agree

Legend: 1 = Certainly Agree; 2 = Agree; 3 = Neutral; 4 = Disagree; 5 = Certainly Disagree

Table 8 shows the weighted mean and standard deviations of the respondents' perception on the coping mechanism. As seen in the table, the grand mean obtained on psycho-social is 1.95 with a standard deviation of 22.23, interpreted as agree. The grand mean in living condition is 2.39 with a standard deviation of 21.53, interpreted as agree. While in financial, it has grand mean of 3.05 with a standard deviation of 15.01, interpreted as neutral. And lastly, in health, it has a grand mean of 2.27 with a standard deviation of 19.33 interpreted as agree.

The data depicted that the respondents agree on the indicators on psycho-social, living condition and health as a coping mechanism towards problems and challenges they faced after the siege. While on financial the respondents were neutral in financial indicators coping mechanism. This means that they neither agree nor disagree that the indicators in financial are the coping mechanism on how they deal on their financial concerns. This further implied that respondents seem to be doing alright on how they coped with psycho-

social, living condition and health challenges and problem. However, the respondents still were uncertain on how they should cope with financial challenges.

The findings are congruent to the Article of Gaglac (2017) emphasized that Local crisis officials have declared a "mental health crisis" among residents affected by the long-drawn conflict here. There were after signs of mental illness manifested in over 30,000 displaced residents. Data from the Integrated Provincial Health Office (IPHO) revealed that as of Aug. 1, at least 30,732 evacuees have manifested mental disorders. Authorities attributed such incidence to the prolonged war, difficulties in living conditions in evacuation centers, and hopelessness as they faced a bleak and dim future.

As stated during the Interview to Ustadz Alimondas Laut, an evacuee from Marawi City, shared his story at the press conference. He and his family members were ordered by the military, on May 24, to leave Marawi City within six hours. If not, they were threatened with reprisals. He said that evacuated safely to Iligan City where they stayed with relatives. Compared to other evacuees who went to overcrowded evacuation centers, he felt a bit luckier. He found Marawi City unrecognizable now, a far cry from the beautiful city it once was. He said corpses of civilians litter Marawi City streets, unrecovered by families who were forcibly evacuated or driven out by fear of aerial strikes.

According to Rev. Irma Balaba of church group Promotion of Church Peoples' Response (PCPR) (2017) lamented the military's use of mosques as forward bases in their battle against the Maute group. Many Muslims, as a result, are unable to hold religious celebration "Sa gerang ito, palaging talo ang mga sibilyan," (In this war it's the civilians who lose out) she said. Lumads suffer under martial law in a statement, Pya Macliing Malayao, Igorot secretary general of indigenous rights group Katribu Kalipunan ng Katutubong Mamamayan ng Pilipinas (KATRIBU) said martial law has been disastrous for Lumad communities in Mindanao.

Conclusions

Generally, the respondents of the study have determined the potential problems and challenges encountered by the selected teacher (Assatidz) and students of Ja'miatul Waqf as an aftermath of Marawi Siege. Firstly, thru the data gathered the respondent agreed on psycho-social simply because after the Marawi Siege there was no psycho-social moral recovery conducted by the government or even voluntarily facilitated by the other private agencies, in order to relieve the agony, they had felt. Secondly, financial condition of the respondents both the Teacher (Assatidz) and students really affect their entire lives simply because teaching is their basic works that sustain their daily lives. Hence, the statements provided by the researcher in the major problems and challenges they faced after the Marawi Siege. Aside from that, the Teacher (Assatidz) and Students responses to the living condition and health they had faced after the siege was neutral which means they neither agree nor disagree that the statements in each category on living condition and health are one of the problems and challenges that they faced after the Marawi siege.

In the study, the researcher has also determined that the coping mechanism towards the problems, challenges of the selected teacher (Assatidz) and students of Ja'miatul Waqf encountered it as an aftermath of Marawi siege. Indubitably thru the data gathered the respondent agreed in psycho-social, living condition and health that the statements provided by the researcher in each category on psycho-social, living condition and health are their coping mechanism towards the problems and challenges they had encountered. Whereas, the respondent's response to the financial condition is neutral. This signifies that they neither agree nor disagree that the statements provided by the researcher under financial are their coping mechanism

Furthermore, it is undeniable that majority of the respondents are very assertive in their opinion that psycho-social problems and financial situation are their major problems and challenges after the Marawi Siege. However, living condition, health and psycho-social are the solutions to the problems challenges they encountered after the Marawi Siege.

In line with the summary of the findings and Implication of the study the following are hereby recommended;

It is strongly recommended that there should be a regular or extensive moral recovery or psycho-social intervention program to the Teacher (Assatidz) and Students facilitated by the Non- Government Organization or Government of the Philippines. This intervention program is designed to relieve the discomfort of the Teacher (Assatidz) and Student so that it will be easy to forget the agony they had felt during the Marawi Siege.

Likewise, it is highly suggested that there should be more intervention of the Government to all IDP's, not just those who are currently living in the Evacuation Center but all those who are affected in the siege, more specifically the Teachers (Assatidz) and Students of Different Arabic Institution who are also the victims of the siege.

More so it is imperative that there should be a livelihood program of the Local Government unit or the Government as a whole in line with those affected Arabic Teacher (Assatidz) whose income are dependent on their teaching.

It is also suggested that, there should be more attention of the government to regulate the Curriculum of the Traditional Madrasah. This is Due to the Misconception to the teaching of Arabic Institutions in Marawi City. And to erase the issue that Madrasah were a breeding grounds for extremist and terrorist group.

It is highly suggested that individual Muslim Meranaws residing in Islamic City of Marawi should be united in state of necessity. That

they should try to understand their situation and possibly support as well as help each other during crisis.

Lastly, further study should be undertaken in the future seeking the extensive research in order to find out the reality as regards to the living condition and health of students and Assatidz of another Madrasah that are also affected during the Marawi Siege.

References

- Aba, E. (2017) Humanitarian Crisis in Marawi. Available <http://bulatlat.com/main/2017/06/23/marawi-will-truly-flattened-humanitarian-mission-airs-peoples-sentiments-vs-martial-law-govt-airstrikes-mindanao>
- Aliponto, I. (2007). An Assessment on the Ecotourism, Programs/ Projects of the City Government of Marawi City, Masteral Thesis. Marawi City: Mindanao State university.
- Allan, N (2017) Don't Blame Maranao for destruction of Marawi City Available <http://newsinfo.inquirer.net/912743/dont-blame-maranao-for-destruction-of-marawi-city>
- Cayongcat A. 1984 Knowing the Meranaos
- Diamoaden, A. (2014). The Roles of Non-Government Organization (NGO'S) For Peace and Development and its Relation to the Local Government Units: Its Implication to Public Administration, Masteral Thesis. Marawi City, Jamiatul Philippine Al-Islamia.
- Gagalac, R. (2017) Mental Health Crisis Available <http://news.abs-cbn.com/news/11/09/17/retaliatory-bombings-possible-after-marawi-siege-analyst>
- Para, S. and Solaiman, H. (2017) Perception of the Selected Businessmen in Marawi City on the Marawi Siege, Mindanao state University.
- Prudent, A. (2017) Education Failure Marawi madrasah Availabe <https://www.rappler.com/thought-leaders/171584-education-failure-marawi-madrasah>
- Tagoranao, M. and Gamon, A. (2017), The Post-war Reconstruction of Waqf Properties in Marawi City: Prospect and Challenges, International Islamic University Malaysia, Kulliyah of Islamic Revealed Know ledged and Human Sciences 53100 Gombak, Selangor, Malaysia
- Umel, R., Jerusalem J., Aguirre, E., And Lim, F. (2017) accelerate the rehabilitation plan for Marawi City and Lano del sur. Available <http://newsinfo.inquirer.net/916159/martial-law-extension-draw-mixed-reactions-from-mindanaoans>
- Warriers, C. 1972, the Meranao Studies

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Arsalan A. Diamoaden, PhD

Bangsamoro Sports Commission – Philippines